

MEDICAL SCIENCES

FACTORS AND TRENDS IN THE CHOICE OF PROFESSIONAL REALIZATION AMONG STUDENTS OF THE "NURSING" SPECIALTY AT THE MEDICAL UNIVERSITY – SOFIA

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ABSTRACT

The shortage of nurses is a persistent structural problem for Bulgaria's healthcare system, characterized by regional imbalances, an unfavorable age structure, and staff migration. This study aims to analyze the professional aspirations of students majoring in nursing at the Faculty of Public Health at the Medical University of Sofia.

An empirical survey was conducted from September to November of 2025, covering 174 students from all degree programs. Data were collected using a self-developed questionnaire and analyzed using descriptive and statistical methods.

The results reveal a strong preference for professional development in large urban centers, particularly in the capital, and a clear inclination toward inpatient care facilities. There is limited interest in the outpatient sector and small towns. Over half of the respondents expressed an intention to pursue further education after obtaining a bachelor's degree, indicating a high level of motivation for professional and academic development.

These results underscore the necessity of integrated educational and human resources policies that promote sustainable development and an equitable distribution of nursing staff throughout the country.

Keywords: students, nurse, professional realization.

Introduction

Bulgaria is experiencing a chronic shortage of healthcare professionals, with many leaving smaller towns for larger cities and the country for other EU countries. This has led to regional shortages, overburdened staff, and deteriorating access to medical services in some areas. Similar problems are observed in other EU member states because, according to community standards, the health of citizens is one of the union's main priorities. The EU must overcome many challenges to ensure a high level of health and quality healthcare in its member states [1].

The free movement of persons is one of the fundamental freedoms guaranteed by Community law. The free movement of workers is regulated by Article 39 of the EC Treaty and further developed in Regulation 1612/68/EEC [2], which provides for the right of EU citizens to work in another Member State as employees or civil servants. The right of establishment is regulated by Article 43, which provides for the right to work as a self-employed person in another Member State. Article 49 guarantees the right to provide services freely. Regulation (EEC) No 1408/71 and its implementing Regulation (EEC) No 574/72 [3] coordinate the various social security schemes in order to facilitate the exercise of this fundamental right to free movement. EU citizens also have the right to study in another Member State under the same conditions as nationals of that country. Directive 2005/36/EC [4] provides for the

recognition of professional qualifications with a view to establishing oneself in another Member State and with a view to facilitating the provision of cross-border services in a Member State other than that of establishment.

The free movement of students and health professionals creates opportunities for individuals to pursue their careers where they are most needed or where they would find the best conditions for their professional development. Healthcare professionals, and nurses in particular, change their country of residence and work for a variety of reasons: better pay, better career opportunities, career development opportunities, and better working conditions. With this migration of medical personnel, some countries are faced with a shortage of healthcare professionals and low motivation to invest in the education of such personnel, due to their inability to retain them for employment within their territory.

The National Health Strategy 2030 (adopted by the National Assembly, published/updated in 2024–2025) [5] is the main strategic document that sets long-term goals and priorities for the sector, including measures related to human resources—training, career development, digitization, and workforce planning. The document formulates policies for education, recruitment, and distribution of personnel in the health sector.

According to official data from the National Statistical Institute, the number of working nurses in Bulgaria as of December 31, 2024, is 28,392, and the number of practicing doctors is 30,149 [6], which shows that in order to achieve the normal ratio of 2 to 1, the number of nurses in the system needs to increase by at least that much.

A 2025 report by the Institute for Market Economics (IME) research center indicates that the shortage of nurses is ongoing: in recent decades, their numbers have declined by $\approx 10\%$, and after 2020, doctors will outnumber nurses in the country.

According to published EU data, Bulgaria has a significantly lower number of nurses relative to its population than other European Member States. To improve the quality of medical care in Bulgaria, the number of nurses must increase, and they must be motivated to develop their careers in their chosen field in Bulgaria.

Studies on human resources in healthcare have increasingly focused on the quantitative shortage of nurses and trends in their professional development, including preferences for place of work, type of healthcare facility, and opportunities for career and academic development. International analyses show that these trends result from a complex interaction between individual motivational factors, working conditions, and national healthcare policies.

The World Health Organization emphasizes that despite the increase in the number of nurses globally, significant imbalances in their distribution continue to exist, with young professionals heavily concentrated in large urban centers and in the hospital sector. This leads to persistent difficulties in providing health care in smaller towns and in outpatient care [7].

Attitudes toward future professional realization are often formed during training. These attitudes are closely related to the learning process, clinical practice, and perceived prospects for development within the profession. Studying these attitudes provides a deeper understanding of the factors influencing future nurses' professional choices and creates a basis for formulating adequate educational and personnel policies.

The aim of this article is to present and analyze the factors and trends for the future professional realization of students majoring in nursing from all courses

of study at the Faculty of Public Health "Prof. Dr. Tsek-omir Vodenicharov, MD" at the Medical University of Sofia.

Materials and methods of the research:

The subject of the study are students majoring in nursing at the Medical University of Sofia.

The study was conducted between September 2025 and November 2025 in Sofia, with 174 nursing students participating, with a male to female ratio of 5% to 95%.

A wide range of sociological and statistical methods were used in the study: documentary method; questionnaire survey method – nursing students at the Medical University of Sofia were surveyed using an independently developed questionnaire; descriptive analysis; analysis of variance; Pearson's χ^2 test; graphical analysis – to visualize the results obtained. The indicators were assessed at a significance level of $\alpha=0.05$.

The quantitative analyses were performed using the statistical software package SPSS 17.0. MICROSOFT OFFICE products were used for tabular and graphical processing and presentation.

Results and discussion

Medical education is of paramount importance for the country, as it "ensures and guarantees the scope and quality of training of medical professionals, as well as non-medical professionals working in the national healthcare system" (Article 174, paragraph 1 of the Health Act) [8]. The specific nature of higher medical education, the protected status of the nursing profession, and the selection of students influence their socio-demographic profile.

This study covers 174 nursing students in their first, second, third, and fourth years of study. Over 94% of the respondents, or 166 out of 174, indicated that they were female, while 5%, or 8 respondents, indicated that they were male. Although there is no legal or administrative division of students by gender, this major remains highly preferred by women. The demographic characteristics of the surveyed students are presented in Figures 1 and 2.

Fig. 1 shows the marital status of the surveyed students. The largest proportion of students indicated that they were unmarried (53%), one third of students (35%) indicated that they were married, 9% indicated that they were divorced, and 3% indicated that they were widowed.

Fig. 1. What is your marital status?

Figure 1 shows the distribution of nurses surveyed according to their marital status. It also provides important information about the social context in which they pursue their professional careers. The observed distribution shows a predominance of individuals with an established marital status (married), along with a significant proportion of unmarried respondents.

This can be interpreted as an indicator of relative stability in the social and personal lives of many of the respondents, which is directly related to their professional development and retention in the field. Marital status is often associated with a greater need for security, a stable income, and predictability in the work environment. This may explain why many nurses choose careers in the healthcare system despite the well-known difficulties and heavy workload of the profession.

At the same time, the proportion of single nurses should not be considered insignificant. This group is often characterized by higher mobility and readiness for professional change, including migration or a change in work environment. In this sense, the results in Figure 1 can be linked to different strategies for professional fulfillment, depending not only on individual motivation, but also on the life stage of the respondents.

In this context, the presented results highlight the significance of family status in influencing nurses' pro-

fessional decisions and fulfillment. The results highlight the need for differentiated management and personnel policies that consider the various social backgrounds of nurses. Offering flexible work schedules, opportunities to balance professional and family obligations, and a supportive work environment can lead to greater satisfaction and the long-term retention of staff in the healthcare system.

Fig. 2 presents the answers of the surveyed students to the question "What is your education so far?". 44% answer secondary, 33% answer that they have acquired secondary specialised education, 5% or 8 respondents answer that they have a specialisation, 18% or 31 of the 174 respondents indicated that they had completed another higher education program before beginning their nursing studies. Many of the students and subsequent practicing nurses choose nursing not directly after completing their secondary education, but after an initial professional/personal career, or as a conscious desire for a "new beginning" (career change), realizing that it is "their time" [9]. Students who choose this specialty after already having completed higher education have different motivations; they do not simply want to "get a diploma," but to change their profession in search of satisfaction and a lasting vocation.

Fig. 2. What is your education to date?

Figure 2 shows the educational profile of students at the time they enrolled in the nursing program. The distribution of responses indicates a variety of educational trajectories and heterogeneous academic and professional experience among the study group.

The predominance of students who have completed secondary education highlights the traditional path into the nursing profession and underscores the specialty's role as a primary choice for professional development in healthcare. This group typically starts professional development earlier and is more willing to build a long-term career within the system.

Additionally, the presence of students who have already obtained higher or secondary education is a significant analytical focus. This result can be interpreted as an indicator of a conscious professional choice and reorientation toward a profession with clear social significance and stable realization. In these cases, training to become a nurse is not an initial educational choice, but rather a strategic decision related to the search for professional security, real employment, and the practical application of acquired knowledge.

The heterogeneous educational backgrounds of students imply different expectations regarding the learning process and future professional realization. Students with prior education often have accumulated

academic or professional experience, which can facilitate their adaptation to the university environment and clinical practice. However, it can also make them more critical of the content and organization of training.

Regarding the professional development of nurses, the results presented here highlight the significance of educational background in influencing adaptation to the profession, career expectations, and satisfaction levels. The results highlight the need for flexible educational approaches that consider students' diverse backgrounds and foster the development of professional competencies.

Figure 2 supplements the overall picture of professional realization by demonstrating that the nursing profession appeals to young individuals without prior academic experience and to those with an established educational background. This diversity should be viewed as a resource that can contribute to the sustainable development of nursing staff, provided adequate educational and organizational strategies support it.

To examine the respondents' attitudes toward their future careers, they were asked, "In which town would you like to pursue your career after graduation?" (Fig. 3).

Fig. 3. In which town would you like to pursue your career after graduation?

The results presented in Figure 3 outline the preferences of nursing students regarding the type of settlement in which they would like to pursue their career after graduation. 76% or 130 of them respond that they intend to pursue their career in the capital, 18% or 32 intend to work in another city, 4% or 7 respondents say they intend to work abroad, and only 2% or three respondents say they intend to work in a village. The observed pattern shows a division between preferences for large cities, medium-sized cities, and small towns/villages, which reflects both individual expectations and perceptions of working and living conditions.

Analysis of these data shows that a significant proportion of respondents prefer to pursue their careers in larger urban centers. This can be explained by the wider opportunities for professional development, better working conditions, the variety of specializations, and the availability of larger healthcare institutions that provide opportunities for different career paths. For young professionals, cities are often associated not only with professional prospects, but also with the social environment, education, and opportunities for personal development.

The variability in preferences for medium-sized and small towns is also significant. Although they are not the leading choice for most respondents, the presence of students who indicate this type of settlement is not insignificant. The trend may reflect both a personal willingness to work in areas closer to the family environment and opportunities related to certain types of health services outside the major centres.

This dynamic in preferences is consistent with international empirical studies showing that job location is a key component of healthcare professionals' career decisions and is strongly influenced by a combination of personal and organizational factors. For example, a study conducted among registered nurses in the US found that when choosing between positions in urban and more remote (rural) areas, key factors are not only remuneration, but also a supportive work environment, autonomy, and the presence of a cohesive team, with location playing a role in the search for these characteristics and influencing the overall choice of workplace [10].

From the perspective of health systems, preferences for urban jobs can also be linked to the greater concentration of infrastructure, technological resources, and specialized services in large centers, which in turn facilitates practice and continuing professional education. This is particularly important for specialties where constant access to modern clinical practices is a prerequisite for maintaining high professional standards.

At the same time, international literature highlights the challenges of attracting and retaining nurses in smaller and rural areas, where structural resources and social services are often lacking, making it difficult to settle and pursue a long-term career. Thus, health human resource planning strategies include both economic incentives and improvements in working conditions and the living environment in these areas to increase their attractiveness to health professionals [11].

It is important to note that preferences regarding place of residence are not only a matter of personal choice; they often reflect deeper structural factors, such as the quality of health services, the availability of training and specialization opportunities, living conditions, career prospects, and social support. Therefore,

the results in Figure 2 describe current attitudes and outline important political and organizational challenges for health systems.

Figure 4 shows the responses to the question, "Where would you like to work after graduation?"

Fig. 4. Where would you like to work after graduation?

Figure 4 illustrates nursing students' attitudes about where they would like to work after graduation. The distribution of responses shows varying preferences among students regarding their future careers. Eighty-one percent of respondents indicated that they would like to work in hospitals. Eight percent indicated that they would like to work in outpatient care facilities. Six percent indicated that they would like to work in health offices in nurseries or kindergartens. Five percent responded that they would like to work in individual healthcare practices.

One of the key trends that stands out is the clear orientation towards inpatient care facilities. This choice may be influenced by the perception that these environments provide stable employment, better material and professional support, as well as opportunities for specialization and professional development within the system. Similar attitudes were observed in a study conducted among nursing students in Italy, where the majority preferred to work in inpatient care facilities, specifically in clinical areas such as pediatrics, emergency departments, and operating rooms. These preferences remain consistent throughout their years of study and reflect stable patterns of career attitudes related to clinical practice [12].

Job preferences are also often linked to the clinical experience students gain during their training. Research shows that students often choose job positions that resemble those in which they were trained or developed valid professional skills during their internships, which has also been found in the context of choosing between the public and private sectors in other countries [13]. This trend can be explained by the greater sense of security and competence in performing professional tasks in an environment that is familiar from the learning process.

On the other hand, it is possible that some students prefer jobs outside the traditional hospital setting, and such choices may be motivated by personal beliefs about the importance of healthcare in a broader social context, a desire for work-life balance, or a search for more dynamic and patient-oriented roles. The career of nurses is not limited solely to hospital structures – a study focused on home care shows that factors such as job quality, independence, and satisfaction with patient relationships have a strong influence on the choice of working environment in community care areas [14].

It is important to note that the choice of where to work after graduation is not just a matter of professional preference but reflects a broader range of expectations and assessments of the future work environment. This includes perceptions of working conditions, opportunities for continuing education, interaction with colleagues and patients, and opportunities for professional and personal development. Factors such as working hours, geographical location, working conditions, and training opportunities have a strong influence on the preferences of medical professionals when choosing a job, and not just the characteristics of the workplace itself [15].

Figure 4 shows that students' preferences for where to work after graduation are multifaceted. They include a desire for job security and professional development in clinical settings, as well as potential interest in more specialized or community-based roles. This pattern of attitudes provides valuable information for educational institutions and healthcare policymakers interested in directing future nursing staff toward areas with the greatest need for skilled labor.

To examine attitudes toward continuing education after nursing school, respondents were asked, "Do you plan to continue your education after obtaining a bachelor's degree?" (Fig. 5).

Fig. 5. Do you plan to continue your education after obtaining a bachelor's degree?

Figure 5 shows the results of a survey of nursing students regarding their intention to continue their education after obtaining a bachelor's degree. Of the respondents, 56% said they would continue their education, 34% said they had not yet decided, and 10% said they did not intend to do so. These results suggest a significant proportion of students plan to further their education, indicating a desire for professional development and improvement of competencies in the field of healthcare.

The willingness to continue education after graduation is in line with established international trends, according to which nurses increasingly perceive additional qualifications as a key factor for career advancement, professional autonomy, and participation in more specialized clinical, managerial, or educational roles. A survey of registered nurses and midwives found that a significant proportion of respondents expressed a strong intention to continue their education, motivated by a desire to improve their professional skills and expand their opportunities for realization [16].

These results can also be viewed in the context of changing requirements for the nursing profession related to increasing care complexity, new technologies, and interdisciplinary work. Continuing professional and academic training is essential for maintaining the quality of healthcare and adapting nurses to the dynamics of healthcare systems.

However, not all students are willing to pursue continuing education, possibly due to financial constraints, the need for rapid entry into the labor market, family commitments, or a lack of clear prospects for professional growth after obtaining an additional qualification.

Figure 5 shows significant potential for academic and professional development among nursing students. Providing accessible, flexible continuing education and a clear link between higher qualifications and career advancement could encourage more future nurses to invest in their education and professional development.

Conclusions

The results of an empirical study conducted among nursing students at the Faculty of Public Health

at the Medical University of Sofia reveal clearly expressed attitudes and trends regarding their future professional realization. The data show that the choice of the nursing profession is largely conscious and motivated, with students demonstrating a desire for professional security and development within the healthcare system.

Preferences for professional realization are strongly concentrated in large urban centers, particularly in the capital, confirming the existence of persistent regional imbalances in the distribution of nursing staff. The limited interest in working in small towns and rural areas highlights the need for targeted policies to encourage and retain nurses in regions with a shortage of healthcare professionals.

Regarding the working environment after graduation, there is a dominant orientation toward hospital care facilities, which can be explained by perceived opportunities for professional development, specialization, and greater organizational security. The weaker interest in outpatient care and community health highlights the need for these sectors to be more actively presented in the educational process and career guidance of students.

A significant focus of the study is attitudes toward continuing education. More than half of the respondents stated their intention to continue their education after completing their bachelor's degree, while a significant proportion expressed hesitation, indicating the potential for academic and professional development. These results underscore the importance of continuing education in enhancing professional competence and adapting to the evolving demands of the healthcare system.

In conclusion, this study shows that, while nursing students are highly motivated to realize and develop their careers, their attitudes do not fully correspond to the structural needs of the national healthcare system. An integrated approach combining educational, staffing, and social measures is necessary for sustainable development and an even distribution of nursing staff throughout the country.

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